

1 **Title:** An automated low-cost solution for creating a multiple-step thermal gradient to record daily
2 fish thermoregulatory behaviour.

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18 **Abstract**

19 Photoperiod and temperature are two of the most powerful environmental cues that entrain
20 circadian clocks. Being ectothermic, fish must keep their body temperature within a physiological
21 range to optimize biological processes mainly applying behavioural strategies. Here, we developed a
22 low-cost, automated system that allow to create a horizontal thermal gradient and videorecord fish
23 behaviour for long-term periods. To validate the system, we assessed daily thermal preference and
24 locomotor activity in the teleost *Danio rerio*. Our apparatus provides the opportunity to investigate
25 the behavioural thermoregulation of captive fish, and our results highlight the importance of
26 considering thermal preferences when designing husbandry protocols.

27

28 **Keywords:** circadian rhythms, daily activity, thermal preference, welfare, zebrafish

29 **Main Text**

30 Circadian clocks have evolved to allow almost all organisms to entrain their physiological
31 functions and behaviour to cyclic environmental fluctuations.¹⁻⁵ Among these, light and temperature
32 cycles are strictly correlated in the wild, and their daily variations strongly affect biological processes
33 of organisms, such as reproduction, metabolism, spatial distribution, locomotor and feeding
34 behaviour.⁶⁻¹⁰ Ectotherm species exclusively rely on behaviour to actively choose a thermal
35 environment that favours high physiological performance (i.e., behavioural thermoregulation).¹¹⁻¹⁵
36 However, breeding animals are commonly reared at constant environmental temperature, an unnatural
37 condition in which animal can not exploit their natural behaviour. Indeed, recent studies pointed
38 several advantages of the thermoregulation in captive breeding (i.e., decreased cortisol levels, reduced
39 aggressive behaviours, decrease in mortality, oxidative stress and DNA damage) supporting how a
40 thermoregulatory environment allow organism to exploit their behaviour by avoiding stress-induced
41 effects, which improve their welfare.¹⁶⁻¹⁸

42 Over the last 20 years, several systems have been developed to study thermal preference in
43 fish, including the shuttlebox^{19,13} and the annular chamber.^{20,21} The first one consist of cylindrical
44 tanks differing in water temperatures and connected by a narrow tunnel, which allow fish move freely
45 between the tanks. The annular chamber, conversely, consisted of concentric swimming channels
46 where the multi-step thermal gradient was provided by external reservoir connected to the tanks.
47 Given their limited size (i.e. shuttle box) and/or number of connected tanks (i.e. annular chamber),
48 these systems are used to investigate thermal preferences of individual or small group of fish for short
49 periods (Table 1).²²⁻²⁴ To overcome this temporal limitation on long-term behavioural recording,
50 recent studies have developed non-continuous thermal gradient systems, which can allow to study
51 fish thermal preference and their behavioural rhythms in breeding conditions. However, these systems
52 lack of automation and require daily intervention by the experimenter to maintain a constant gradient,
53 potentially arousing stress levels in fish (Table 1).^{25,15,26} Here, we describe an automated-recording,
54 low-cost and user-friendly-interface solution to investigate daily thermal preferences and locomotor

55 activity in fish (Fig. 1). Briefly, two separate automatic systems/components were used i) to
56 generate/regulate water temperature in a multi-chamber tank by heater-cooler systems and ii) to
57 acquire data of fish behaviour for long period by producing high-quality video recordings. Our
58 multiple-step thermal gradient is automatically controlled by a microcontroller board based on the
59 ATmega2560 (e.g., Arduino, <https://www.arduino.cc/>); an open-source platform that can be easily
60 programmed to control water temperatures using dedicated probes.²⁷ Specifically, probes, heaters and
61 pumps were placed in each chamber of the tank that composes the system (Fig. 1A). The probe
62 measures the water temperature and sends the acquired information to the microcontroller, which
63 switches the heater in each chamber on or off to maintain the pre-set thermal gradient (Fig. 1Ai; see
64 details in Supplementary Materials §2). In addition, small pumps recirculate the water without
65 creating turbulence, which could affect the following video-analysis, and prevent the formation of a
66 vertical temperature gradient in each chamber (see details in Supplementary Materials §2).
67 Furthermore, each chamber presented these three components to prevent fish from developing a
68 preference for a spatial arrangement rather than a temperature preference. The video recording system
69 is based on the raspberry pi (Fig. 1Aii); a small, single-board computer highly customisable
70 programming capabilities, that provides an effective, low-cost solution.²⁸

71 To validate the efficacy of the system for studying behavioural rhythms, daily thermal
72 preference and locomotor activity, the behaviour of the model teleost *Danio rerio* were continuously
73 recorded for at least 4 complete days (N = 12 fish/system; three systems in total; see details in
74 Supplementary Materials §3). The multiple-step temperature gradient was set at 24 - 32 °C according
75 to the physiology of the species.²⁹ Repeated measures ANOVA analysis on the pooled dataset found
76 a significant temporal fluctuation across *Zeitgeber* Time (ZT) in both thermal preferences (Linear
77 Mixed Effect Model, effect of the covariate “ZT”: $F_{1,108} = 203.450$, $P < 0.001$) and distance covered
78 ($F_{1,108} = 109.090$, $P < 0.001$; see details in Supplementary Materials §5). Cosinor analysis^{30,31}
79 confirmed the presence of daily rhythmicity in the thermal preference and distance covered across

80 days in each system (Table S1). Fish showed a significant daily rhythm in their preferred temperatures
81 (zero-amplitude test: $F_{2,111} = 48.726$, $P < 0.001$; Fig. 1B) by selecting higher temperatures during the
82 day and lower temperatures during the night with a diurnal acrophase, i.e. the peak of their daily
83 thermal preference rhythm, at $ZT 6.10 \pm 0.54$ (Table S1). Being a diurnal species, zebrafish also
84 displayed a significant daily rhythm of activity ($F_{2,111} = 267.7951$, $P < 0.001$; Fig. 1C; Table S1), with
85 more than 80% of locomotor activity (85.17 ± 1.50 %, mean \pm SD) during the light phase and a mean
86 acrophase at the middle of the light phase ($ZT 6.38 \pm 0.17$; Table S1).

87 In conclusion, our system offers an automatic low-cost and user-friendly solution for studying
88 daily rhythmicity of thermal preferences in several fish species. The main novelty of this system lies
89 in the automation of its components, less intervention by the investigator and, consequently, less
90 stressful events for the captive fish (Table 1). Additionally, our system provides behavioural
91 parameters, such as daily activity, which could serve as potential welfare indicators for laboratory
92 and farm fish.^{18,32} Finally, the system might be applied in chronobiology studies requiring long-term
93 recordings to investigate the effects of relevant synchronizers, such as light and temperature, on fish
94 physiology and behaviour in breeding conditions.^{1,4}

95 These behavioural and physiological parameters could be used for improving husbandry
96 protocols, by applying daily thermocycles, to refine breeding conditions.^{33,34} Furthermore, by
97 exploiting its automation, our system can potentially be used in laboratories to manipulate water
98 temperature as required by species-specific fish needs. Finally, the investigation of daily
99 thermoregulation in fish will provide new accurate and consistent data about the thermal biology of
100 ectotherms and how temperature linked to photoperiod can entrain circadian clocks in fish in a
101 dynamically changing world. Climate change and the consequent global warming impacts fish
102 ecophysiology limiting their performance and fitness.^{35,36} Being able to replicate such extreme
103 conditions in the laboratory by manipulating water temperature and studying the resulting behavioural

104 thermoregulation could be significant for understanding the future impacts of global warming on
105 ecosystems.

106 **Data availability statement**

107 The Practical Guide to realize the system and the software for video-acquiring are available
108 in the Supplementary Material and in the Git-hub page
109 <https://github.com/CristianoBertolucci/FishTemperatureGradientSystem>.

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118 **Authorship contribution statement**

119 **F. Conti:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Data Curation, Writing - Original
120 Draft, Writing - Review & Editing, Visualization; **G. de Alba:** Conceptualization, Methodology,
121 Writing - Review & Editing; **J.F. López-Olmeda:** Conceptualization, Writing - Review & Editing;
122 **L. M. Vera:** Conceptualization, Writing - Review & Editing; **G. Lucon-Xiccato:** Software, Writing
123 - Review & Editing; **E. Mainardi:** Methodology, Writing - Review & Editing, Visualization; **S.**
124 **Cesari:** Methodology, Writing - Review & Editing, Visualization; **M. Bottarelli:** Methodology,
125 Writing - Review & Editing, Visualization; **C. Bertolucci:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing
126 - Original Draft, Writing - Review & Editing, Visualization, Funding acquisition; **F.J. Sánchez-**
127 **Vázquez:** Conceptualization, Writing - Review & Editing, Funding acquisition; **E. Gatto:**

128 Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Formal analysis, Investigation, Data Curation, Writing -
129 Original Draft, Writing - Review & Editing, Visualization, Funding acquisition.

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131 **Declaration of interests**

132 The authors declare no competing interests.

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134 **References**

- 135 1. Panda S, Hogenesch JB, Kay SA. Circadian rhythms from flies to human. *Nature*
136 2002;417(6886):329-35; doi: 10.1038/417329a
- 137 2. Bertolucci C, Foà A. Extraocular photoreception and circadian entrainment in
138 nonmammalian vertebrates. *Chronobiol Int* 2004;21(4-5):501-19; doi: 10.1081/CBI-
139 120039813
- 140 3. Bell-Pedersen D, Cassone VM, Earnest DJ, et al. Circadian rhythms from multiple
141 oscillators: lessons from diverse organisms. *Nat Rev Genet* 2005;6(7):544-56; doi:
142 <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrg1633>
- 143 4. Krylov VV, Izvekov EI, Pavlova VV, et al. Circadian rhythms in zebrafish (*Danio rerio*)
144 behaviour and the sources of their variability. *Biol Rev Camb Philos Soc* 2021;96(3):785-
145 797; doi: 10.1111/brv.12678
- 146 5. Mazur M, Rakus K, Adamek M, et al. Effects of light and circadian clock on the antiviral
147 immune response in zebrafish. *Fish Shellfish Immunol* 2023;140:108979;
148 doi:10.1016/j.fsi.2023.108979
- 149 6. Refinetti R, Susalka SJ. Circadian rhythm of temperature selection in a nocturnal lizard.
150 *Physiol Behav* 1997;62(2):331-6; doi:10.1016/S0031-9384(97)88989-5

- 151 7. Angilletta Jr MJ, Niewiarowski PH, Navas CA. The evolution of thermal physiology in
152 ectotherms. *J Therm Biol* 2002;27(4):249-268, doi:10.1016/S0306-4565(01)00094-8
- 153 8. Kaneko H, Head LM, Ling J, et al. Circadian rhythm of temperature preference and its
154 neural control in *Drosophila*. *Curr Biol* 2012;22(19):1851-1857; doi:
155 10.1016/j.cub.2012.08.006
- 156 9. Paaijmans KP, Heinig RL, Seliga RA, et al. Temperature variation makes ectotherms more
157 sensitive to climate change. *Glob Chang Biol* 2013;19(8):2373-80; doi:
158 10.1111/gcb.12240
- 159 10. Kern P, Cramp RL, Franklin CE. Physiological responses of ectotherms to daily
160 temperature variation. *J Exp Biol* 2015;218(19):3068-76; doi: 10.1242/jeb.123166
- 161 11. Reynolds WW, Casterlin ME. Behavioral thermoregulation and the “final preferendum”
162 paradigm. *Am Zool* 1979;19(1):211-22; doi: 10.1093/icb/19.1.211
- 163 12. Volkoff H, Rønnestad I. Effects of temperature on feeding and digestive processes in fish.
164 *Temperature* 2020;7(4):307-320; doi: 10.1080/23328940.2020.1765950
- 165 13. Christensen EAF, Norin T, Tabak I, et al. Effects of temperature on physiological
166 performance and behavioral thermoregulation in an invasive fish, the round goby. *J Exp*
167 *Biol* 2021;224(1):jeb237669; doi: 10.1242/jeb.237669.
- 168 14. Gomez-Maldonado S, Camacho-Cervantes M. Effect of a temperature gradient on the
169 behaviour of an endangered Mexican topminnow and an invasive freshwater fish. *Sci Rep*
170 2022;12:20584; doi: 10.1038/s41598-022-24755-9
- 171 15. Vera LM, de Alba G, Santos S, et al. Circadian rhythm of preferred temperature in fish:
172 Behavioural thermoregulation linked to daily photocycles in zebrafish and Nile tilapia. *J*
173 *Therm Biol* 2023;113:103544; doi: 10.1016/j.jtherbio.2023.103544

- 174 16. Huntingford F, Rey S, Quaggiotto MM. Behavioural fever, fish welfare and what farmers
175 and fishers know. *Appl Ani Behav Sci* 2020;231:105090; doi:
176 10.1016/j.applanim.2020.105090
- 177 17. Sanhueza N, Donoso A, Aguilar A, et al. Thermal Modulation of Monoamine Levels
178 Influence Fish Stress and Welfare. *Front Endocrinol* 2018;9:717; doi:
179 10.3389/fendo.2018.00717
- 180 18. Sanhueza N, Fuentes R, Aguilar A, et al. Behavioral Thermoregulation in Captive Fish:
181 Molecular, Physiological, and Welfare Implications. *bioRxiv* 2023; doi:
182 10.1101/2023.10.10.561692
- 183 19. Macnaughton CJ, Kovachik C, Charles C, et al. Using the shuttlebox experimental design
184 to determine temperature preference for juvenile Westslope Cutthroat Trout
185 (*Oncorhynchus clarkii lewisi*). *Conserv Physiol* 2018;6(1):coy018; doi:
186 10.1093/conphys/coy018
- 187 20. Myrick CA, Folgner DK., Cech Jr JJ. An annular chamber for aquatic animal preference
188 studies. *T Am Fish Soc* 2004; 133:427-433.
- 189 21. Reiser S, Temming A, Eckhardt A, et al. Automation and critical evaluation of an annular
190 chamber for aquatic ectotherm temperature preference experiments. *Methods Ecol Evol*
191 2013;4(6):531-541; doi: 10.1111/2041-210X.12045
- 192 22. Cocherell DE, Fangué NA, Klimley PA, et al. Temperature preferences of hardhead
193 *Mylopharodon conocephalus* and rainbow trout *Oncorhynchus mykiss* in an annular
194 chamber. *Environ Biol Fishes* 2014;97:865-873; doi: 10.1007/s10641-013-0185-8

- 195 23. Elsner RA, Shrimpton JM. Behavioural changes during the parr-smolt transformation in
196 coho salmon *Oncorhynchus kisutch*: is it better to be cool? J Fish Biol 2019;95(3):793-
197 801; doi: 10.1111/jfb.14069
- 198 24. Harman AA, Fuzzen M, Stoa L, et al. Evaluating tank acclimation and trial length for
199 dynamic shuttle box temperature preference assays in aquatic animals. J Exp Biol 2021;
200 224(12):jeb233205; doi: 10.1242/jeb.233205
- 201 25. Rey S, Digka N, MacKenzie S. Animal Personality Relates to Thermal Preference in Wild-
202 Type Zebrafish, *Danio rerio*. Zebrafish 2015;12(3):243-249; doi: 10.1089/zeb.2014.107
- 203 26. de Alba G, Conti F, Sánchez J, et al. Effect of light and feeding regimes on the daily rhythm
204 of thermal preference in Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*). Aquaculture 2024;
205 578:740122; doi: 10.1016/j.aquaculture.2023.740122
- 206 27. Ismailov AS, Jo‘Rayev ZB. Study of arduino microcontroller board. Sci Educ
207 2022;3(3):172-179.
- 208 28. Jolles JW. Broad-scale applications of the Raspberry Pi: A review and guide for biologists.
209 Methods Ecol Evol 2021;12(9):1562-1579; doi: 10.1111/2041-210X.13652
- 210 29. López-Olmeda JF, Sánchez-Vázquez FJ. Thermal biology of zebrafish (*Danio rerio*). J
211 Therm Biol 2011;36(2):91-104; doi: 10.1016/j.jtherbio.2010.12.005
- 212 30. Refinetti R, Lissen GC, Halberg F. Procedures for numerical analysis of circadian rhythms.
213 Biol Rhythm Res 2007;38(4):275-325; doi: 10.1080/09291010600903692
- 214 31. Cornelissen G. Cosinor-based rhythmometry. Theor Biol Med Model 2014;11:16; doi:
215 10.1186/1742-4682-11-16

- 216 32. Noble C, Gismervik K, Iversen MH, et al. Welfare Indicators for farmed Atlantic salmon:
217 tools for assessing fish welfare. Nofima: Tromsø, Norway; 2018.
218 <http://hdl.handle.net/11250/2575780>
- 219 33. Toni M, Manciocco A, Angiulli E, et al. Review: Assessing fish welfare in research and
220 aquaculture, with a focus on European directives. *Animal* 2019;13(1):161-170; doi:
221 10.1017/S1751731118000940
- 222 34. Pavlidis M, Papaharisis L, Adamek M, et al. Research for PECH Committee-Animal
223 welfare of farmed fish. Belgium; Retrieved from
224 <https://coilink.org/20.500.12592/mv196q> on 19 Nov 2024. COI: 20.500.12592/mv196q.
- 225 35. Alfonso S, Gesto M, Sadoul B. Temperature increase and its effects on fish stress
226 physiology in the context of global warming. *J Fish Biol* 2021;98(6):1496-1508; doi:
227 10.1111/jfb.14599
- 228 36. McKenzie DJ, Geffroy B, Farrell AP. Effects of global warming on fishes and fisheries. *J*
229 *Fish Biol* 2021;98(6):1489-1492; doi: 10.1111/jfb.14762

230 **Table**

231 Table 1. Summary of the main set up used for studying thermal preference in fish and aquatic
232 organisms.

Apparatus	Hardware and software to control water temperature	Potential exploitation and limits
Shuttle box ^{13,19} (Loligo® Systems)	Automatically controlled	Conditioning, spontaneous temperature preference experiments but for a short time and for a limited temperature range and one/few subjects can be tested.
Annular chambers ^{20,21}	Automatically controlled	Conditioning, spontaneous temperature preference experiments but there may be certain pitfalls regarding chamber dimensioning, thermal stratification, water flux and object detection with the software used.
Non-continuous step-thermal gradient multi-chambered tank ^{15,25, 26}	Manually controlled	Conditioning, spontaneous thermal preference and fish rearing but it may require at least daily intervention by the experimenter for both thermal gradient control and video recordings.
Automated controlled step-thermal gradient multi-chambered tank	Automatically controlled	Conditioning, spontaneous thermal preference experiments and fish rearing. The system we propose allows both the automatic control of the thermal gradient to be created depending on the species and the remote triggering of behavioural video recordings, thus avoiding potentially invasive interventions by the experimenter.

233

234 **Figure caption.**

235 Figure 1: (A) Overview of the automated-recording, low-cost and user-friendly-interface solution
236 for investigating daily variation of thermal preferences in fish. (i) The step-thermal gradient in the
237 multi-chamber tank was created by continuously monitoring the temperature and switching on/off
238 the heater in each compartment via a microcontroller. (ii) Fish behaviour was automatically
239 recorded via a remotely-controlled raspberry pi. (B) Average daily thermal preference and (C)
240 distance covered of *Danio rerio* exposed to a step-thermal gradient of the three systems (N = 12
241 fish/systems) across four completed days of videorecording. Data points represented mean \pm
242 standard deviation of parameters measured each day. Dotted lines represented the 95% confidential
243 interval predicted from the least squares linear regression of Cosinor model. Biological rhythms
244 parameters (i.e., Mesor, Amplitude and Acrophase) were reported as mean \pm standard deviation.
245 The white and black bars above graphs represent the light and dark phases, respectively. The time
246 scale (x-axis) is expressed as *Zeitgeber* Time (ZT), in which ZT0 corresponds to lights on and ZT14
247 corresponds to lights off. Created with BioRender.com.

A)

B)

C)

